

The Integration of Various Distributed Energy Sources (DES) in Power Distribution Network under Abnormal Conditions using Artificial Intelligence (AI) approach: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT:-Enhancing reliability, efficiency, and sustainability through the integration of various distributed energy sources (DES) into power distribution networks is a revolutionary approach. The present research investigates how power distribution networks perform when various distributed energy sources (DES) are incorporated, such as solar photovoltaic (PV), wind turbines, battery storage systems, and Combined heat and power (CHP) systems. In particular, how adequately technologies like smart grids, Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, and AI/ML-based control systems are used to track, evaluate, and improve the distribution system's response to these challenges is analyzed. The research reviews important performance parameters including voltage stability, power quality, and fault tolerance by modeling numerous abnormal events. The results illustrate that under abnormal conditions such as faults, load variations, and supply disruptions, a well-integrated DES network supported by cutting-edge technologies significantly improves the resilience and adaptability of power distribution Networks. The present research offers valuable perspectives on using smart grids in real-world scenarios. It highlights the critical function that cutting-edge technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) play in supporting a robust and environmentally friendly energy network.

Keywords:- Reliability, Integration, Distributed Energy Sources (DES), Solar Photovoltaic (PV), Wind Turbines, Battery Storage Systems, Smart Grids, Internet Of Things, AI/ML

I.INTRODUCTION

The use of renewables is growing rapidly. Electricity generation from renewable sources, such as hydropower, wind, and solar PV, is expected to increase significantly globally over the next two years, by 8% in 2021 and by more than 6% in 2022, based on present policy settings and economic trends. [2] However, the latest IEA analysis estimates that even with this rapid growth, renewables will only be able to supply around half of the expected rise in global energy consumption over those two years. Over 30% of the power produced comes from renewable sources. 12% of the heat

produced by renewable sources would be used to fuel small-scale energy generation connected to distribution networks. Figure 1 displays 10% of transport energy from renewable sources.

Figure 1. Illustrates the percentage of energy used for electricity generation.

As a result, the use of "clean" generating technologies and renewable energy has increased significantly, while the usage of fossil fuels (such as coal, diesel, and gasoline) has decreased significantly.

[1]. Large-scale integration of decarbonized home heating (such as electric heating pumps) and electrified transportation (such as electric cars and rail electrification) is being pushed for, which will raise the energy demand. With these things taken into account, it is predicted that by 2050, the power demand may have doubled.[2] This will necessitate considerable advancements in electric power systems in order to preserve a reliable, safe, and sustainable energy source. [3]. The final step in the delivery of electricity is the power distribution network. From the transmission system, electricity is delivered to individual consumers. Power outages in an electrical network can occur for a variety of causes. Some of these causes include short circuits, the operation of fuses or circuit breakers, and damage to electric transmission lines, substations, or other distribution system components. [4]. There are now several documented instances of large-scale blackouts, which invariably cause damage in terms of length and effect on loads. Even while it is impossible to completely prevent these kinds of events, it is still possible to manage a power outage well and lessen its detrimental impacts.[5] This paper includes a comprehensive literature review on the performance analysis of power distribution networks with the integration of various distributed energy sources (DES) under abnormal conditions using an Artificial Intelligence (AI) approach. The increasing need for renewable energy sources has led to a rise in the integration of distributed energy systems (DES) into power distribution networks. Artificial

intelligence (AI) techniques can be applied to improve the stability, efficiency, and reliability of power distribution systems.[6]. This research review discusses the various AI techniques employed in analyzing the performance of power distribution networks with integrated DES under abnormal conditions, such as faults and fluctuations in energy generation. The insights gained from this review are valuable for researchers and practitioners in the field of power systems engineering. In this paper Section II Faults on the power distribution network, Section III Conventional Methods, Section IV Proposed Method, and Section V Concludes.

II. FAULTS ON POWER DISTRIBUTION NETWORK

The power distribution network is a system that delivers electricity from power plants to homes, businesses, and other users. It consists of transmission lines, substations, distribution lines, and transformers that work together to ensure a reliable supply of electricity to consumers [7&9]. Several common faults can occur on a power distribution network, including:

- i Short circuit: When two or more conductors come into direct touch with one another, an abrupt spike in electrical current results in a short circuit. This may result in equipment damage, overheating, and possible fires or explosions.
- ii **Overload:** An overload occurs when the electrical load on a circuit exceeds its capacity, causing the wires and components to overheat. This can lead to equipment failure and potential safety hazards.
- iii **Ground fault:** A ground fault occurs when an electrical current flows through a path other than the intended circuit, such as through a person or a conductive material.

This can be dangerous, as it can lead to electric shock or fires.

- iv **Open circuit:** When there is a gap in the electrical route that stops current from flowing, the result is an open circuit. Power outages and electrical system interruptions may result from this.
- v **Voltage sag or dip:** A voltage sag or dip occurs when the voltage levels drop below the normal range, leading to the dimming of lights and potential damage to sensitive equipment.
- vi **Transient voltage:** Transient voltage spikes or surges are sudden, brief increases in voltage levels that can damage equipment and cause system failures.

Figure 2 illustrates the power distribution network.

Figure 2: Power Distribution Network

A review of the literature revealed that faults account for over 80% of power distribution network outages [10, 11]. A circuit breaker at the main feeder will cut off the source from the main feeder in the event of a fault at the feeder laterals or anywhere else along the feeder. Customers who are solely connected to the main feeder will therefore encounter a power loss. The power supply's quality has deteriorated because of this power outage. To reduce the effects of the fault, power outage, and interruption time, the utility must locate the fault as soon as feasible. Distribution networks are susceptible to four primary types of problems.

[12]. These four types of faults are line-to-line (LLF), double line-to-ground (DLGF), single line-to-ground (SLGF), and three-phase line-to-ground (LLLGF). The current magnitude of the fault and its potential to cause damage can be used to express the fault severity. The most serious to-ground failure in power networks occurs when there is simultaneous [13, 14]. Table 1 displays the percentage occurrence of each fault category as well as its severity.

Sort of Fault	% of Occurrence	Severity
SLGF	70%	Less severe
LLF	15%	Less severe
DLGF	10%	Less severe
LLLGF	5%	More severe

Table 1. The percentage occurrence of each fault type and its severity.

Table 2 presents the percentage of fault occurrences attributed to different power system components.

Power System Element	Percentage of fault occurrence
Transformers	10
Overhead lines	50
Underground cables	9
Switchgear	12
CT, PT relays, control equipment, etc.,	12
Generators	7

Table 2. Fault occurrences due to power system elements.

Despite being an essential part of contemporary life, the electrical system is mostly susceptible to blackouts, cascade failures, and natural calamities. Numerous natural calamities, including windstorms, earthquakes, floods, hurricanes, lightning strikes, and wildfires, pose a threat to the

power system [15]. The effects of natural disasters on power distribution networks are depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The impacts of natural disasters on power distribution networks.

Faults on a power distribution network can pose significant risks to the reliability and safety of the electrical system. Utilities need to identify, address, and mitigate these faults to prevent damage to equipment, power outages, and potential safety hazards [16]. Regular maintenance, monitoring, and investment in technology and infrastructure are essential to ensuring a resilient and efficient power distribution network.

III. CONVENTIONAL METHODS

Some of the previous technologies and methodologies that have been used in the field of power distribution networks with the integration of various distributed energy sources (DES) under abnormal conditions include:

I. Traditional power system analysis techniques: These include methods such as load flow analysis, fault analysis, and transient stability analysis, which have been widely used to study the performance of power distribution networks under normal and abnormal conditions.[17]

II. Conventional control and protection strategies: Traditional control and protection strategies have been employed to manage the operation of power distribution networks with the integration

of DES, but these methods may not be sufficient to address the complexities and uncertainties associated with renewable energy sources.

III. Model predictive control (MPC): MPC is a control strategy that uses predictive models to optimize the performance of power distribution networks with DES integration under different operating conditions. It can help in improving the stability and efficiency of the system.

IV. Optimization techniques: The functioning of power distribution networks with DES in unusual circumstances has been optimized through the application of a variety of optimization techniques, including genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, and metaheuristic algorithms, as listed below.

A. Heuristic Search Algorithm: To quickly and effectively discover a solution in today's power distribution networks, two heuristic methods are given [18]. It provides switch selection indices based on an analytical approach and a workable heuristic graph-based strategy for resolving the service restoration problem in distribution networks. Four distinct objective functions are included in the problem formulation.

- i. maximizing the total load that is restored;
- ii. reducing the amount of switching operations;
- iii. maximizing the restored load that is in the highest priority;
- iv. minimizing load shedding

B. Genetic Algorithm: Finding errors is another intelligent application for a genetic algorithm (GA). To pinpoint the precise position, the approach uses selection, crossover, and mutation processes to look for potential fault locations [19]. In Figure 4, the GA algorithm is displayed.

Figure 4. Flowchart of Genetic Algorithm
This approach has the advantage of increasing simulation speed while decreasing the number of viable solutions. Since nearly every operation in GA is random, the results are not constant over time, which is a drawback for fault location in distribution systems. Because GA could yield erroneous results, it might not be appropriate to use this method for online analysis. [20].

V. Machine learning techniques: Neural networks, support vector machines, and decision trees are a few examples of machine learning techniques that have been used to forecast anomalous system behavior and assess the effectiveness of power distribution networks with DES integration. These previous technologies have laid the groundwork for the development and implementation of AI approaches for analyzing the performance of power distribution networks with integrated DES under abnormal conditions. The following are the research gaps Identified from the literature survey.

i. Heuristic search algorithm: It isn't the best one for the performance of the power

distribution network. The disadvantage of hierarchical clustering is that it is relatively slow.

ii. Genetic Algorithm: It is computationally expensive i.e., time-consuming. The results of fault location are not consistent over time because, in GA, almost all processes are random.

iii. Grid Stability and Power Quality: The variability and intermittency of renewable energy sources like solar and wind can lead to challenges in maintaining grid stability and power quality. Issues may arise due to voltage and frequency variations caused by the integration of distributed energy resources.

iv. Faults and Protection: Designing and coordinating electrical system protection with distributed energy resources poses challenges, especially in detecting faults and ensuring protection.

v. Islanding: Ensuring network areas can operate independently as islands in case of grid disconnection requires careful system design and coordination.

vi. Regulatory and Policy Framework Challenges: Current regulatory environments might not fully support the integration of distributed energy onto the grid, posing a challenge for utilities. Collaboration between utilities and regulators is essential to address challenges, protect revenue streams, and support customers' interest in DES.

vii. Technological Integration Challenges: Grid operators face challenges in integrating various distributed energy resources while maintaining grid stability and power quality. Distributed generation sources require careful consideration to ensure they do not disrupt the grid operations or cause voltage fluctuations.

The integration of various Distributed Energy Sources in power distribution networks under abnormal conditions using an AI approach faces significant challenges related to grid stability, power quality, protection systems, regulatory frameworks, and technological integrations. Addressing these challenges will require a holistic approach involving technological innovations, regulatory reforms, and collaborative efforts between utilities, regulators, and other stakeholders in the energy sector.

IV. PROPOSED TECHNOLOGY

Based on the literature survey, the major objectives of the integration of various Distributed Energy Sources (DES) in a Power Distribution Network under Abnormal Conditions using an Artificial Intelligence (AI) approach include Operation and Control Techniques, Power Quality Improvement, Protection & Fault Management, Operational Stability and Advanced Automation and Intelligent Control. By integrating AI approaches with distributed energy sources in power distribution networks under abnormal conditions, these objectives aim to enhance system efficiency, reliability, power quality, protection mechanisms, and overall grid stability, providing a foundation for advanced grid management and optimization to be achieved by the proposed system.

Distributed Energy Sources: Small, modular energy generation and storage systems that generate less than 10 megawatts of power are known as distributed energy sources, or DES. These devices can function independently or be linked to the nearby electrical grid. Various types of distributed energy sources (DES) can be integrated into a power distribution network, each with its

unique characteristics and behavior as follows;

i. Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems: Solar PV systems convert sunlight into electricity through the use of solar panels. Their output is variable and depends on factors such as weather conditions, time of day, and shading. Solar PV systems typically generate electricity during daylight hours when the sun is shining.[21]

ii. Wind turbines: Wind turbines convert wind energy into electricity through the rotation of turbine blades. Wind power generation is variable and depends on wind speed and direction. Wind turbines typically generate more electricity during periods of higher wind speeds.[22]

iii. Energy storage systems: Energy storage systems, such as batteries, pumped hydro storage, and flywheels, store excess energy for later use. They can help balance supply and demand, reduce grid congestion, and provide backup power during outages. The behavior of energy storage systems depends on their capacity, charge/discharge rates, and efficiency.[23]

iv. Combined heat and power (CHP) systems: CHP systems generate both electricity and heat from a single fuel source, such as natural gas or biomass. They are highly efficient and can provide both electricity and thermal energy for heating and cooling applications.

Each type of distributed energy source has its unique behavior and characteristics, which can impact grid operations, electricity pricing, and overall system reliability. Effective integration and management of DES require careful planning, coordination, and technological solutions to optimize their performance and maximize their benefits for the power distribution network.[24] The block diagram of the proposed system is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The block diagram of the proposed system.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a critical role in integrating various Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) for power distribution networks by incorporating real-time data from grid infrastructure, market pricing, supply, demand, load profiles, and weather forecasts as follows;

i. Monitoring and Managing Distributed Devices: AI and Machine Learning (ML) are used to monitor and control hundreds of distinct distributed devices, and algorithms are used. Ensuring consistent participation and proactive management to enhance grid stability [25]

ii. Dynamic Tracking of Flexibility: AI enables the dynamic tracking and forecasting of flexibility available from each resource and aggregating capacities to optimize resource utilization, maintain grid stability, and reduce costs.

iii. Optimization of DES Asset Interaction: In order to accomplish grid objectives and balance supply and demand in real-time, artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms optimize the mix of DES asset categories, including solar PV panels, battery storage systems, and electric vehicles.

[26].

iv. Real-Time Decision-Making and Control: AI technologies allow for real-time decision-making in managing Distributed Energy Resources Management Systems (DERMS), enabling rapid responses to grid conditions, optimizing energy flows, and ensuring seamless coordination across Virtual Power Plants (VPPs). [27]

vi. Large-Scale Energy Forecasting and Management: AI's ability to analyze extensive datasets from millions of DERs enables accurate predictions of energy demand and generation patterns, improving energy forecasting and management.

By harnessing AI technologies, utilities, and energy organizations can optimize the integration of DERs into power distribution networks, improve grid stability, enhance operational efficiency, and drive sustainability goals in the energy sector.

V.CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the literature review on the integration of various Distributed Energy Sources (DES) in power distribution networks using AI approaches highlights the significant impact of AI/ML technologies in enhancing power distribution networks' operational efficiency, reliability, and resilience under abnormal conditions. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies play a transformative role in power distribution networks by enhancing efficiency, reliability, and innovation through their applications in fault detection/protection, state estimation, renewable energy/load forecasting, and other operational aspects. The effectiveness of Machine Learning (ML) today is attributed to factors like increased computational power, greater data

availability, innovative algorithms, and advanced tools. These advancements have enabled the successful application of AI/ML techniques, especially in deep learning, for various tasks. Supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning are the three primary categories of machine learning techniques, and each has a particular function in power distribution network applications. For managing complicated systems, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) such as Recurrent GNNs and Convolutional GNNs are essential like power grids, enabling structured learning and analysis of relationships among components. Ensuring the safe, secure, and trustworthy implementation of AI/ML technologies in power distribution networks is critical for system stability and reliability. Guidelines and standards set by regulatory bodies and government initiatives are crucial for fostering safe AI adoption in power generation, transmission, and distribution networks. Efforts to ensure the safe and secure implementation of AI/ML in grid systems and ongoing research initiatives signify a promising future for the integration of advanced technologies in power distribution networks. The integration of AI/ML applications in power distribution networks offers immense potential for addressing challenges such as the transition to decarbonized energy production, grid resilience, and enhanced operational efficiency. Continued research supported by programs like the DOE-OE AGM program is essential for further advancements in this domain.

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